

Jurayev O.R.
assistant
Department of Agribusiness and Marketing
Andijan Institute of Agriculture and Agrotechnologies
Kamoliddinov Sh.L.
3rd year student of group 67
Agrobusiness and investment activity educational direction

PROBLEMS IN TEACHING ECONOMICS IN HIGHER EDUCATION COUNTRIES

Abstract. Nowadays, learning and studying are considered an important component of every person's life. It consists in mastering the knowledge and experiences created throughout the history of mankind and specially selected for mastering, improving knowledge, skills and abilities. For the implementation of teaching activities, the educational system is organized as a special activity, and in this process, each learner achieves certain goals and tasks of social importance.

In recent years, the number of higher educational institutions in our republic has increased dramatically, branches of foreign higher education institutions have been opened, and the number of specialties in existing institutions has increased. This, in turn, leads to increased competition between educational institutions.

Due to this, today, a lot of attention is paid to improving the quality of education in the higher education system.

Key words: specialist's competence, in the educational process, production, distribution, exchange and consumption of products.

Several theories of teaching have been developed by experts for several hundred years, some of them can be applied today to all educational subjects and objects, and others to specific subjects or to certain types of educational institutions. These theories determine and describe the main important signs and characteristics of the educational process determined by the subject being studied. Due to the changes taking place in the society at the present time, the teaching of social sciences has its own characteristics. Because most of the social sciences, especially the areas of economics, unlike the natural sciences, react very sharply to the changes in social life.

Therefore, the method of teaching economic sciences is a field of social relations, which consists in studying a set of interrelated means, methods and forms of teaching economic sciences. The peculiarity of this method is that it is closely related to the economic life of society, more specifically, to the

production, distribution, exchange and consumption of products. Activity for formation implies the active use of the name in practical terms.

It is known that teaching methods have a strong influence on the effectiveness of the educational process. Due to this, the level of preparation and effectiveness of education directly depends on the interaction between the teacher and the student.

Today, the demand for economic knowledge by the society requires a creative approach to the educational process from both the teacher and the student.

Because it is very important for a student to learn to act freely in not only simulated but also real economic processes and adapt to it. Teaching students to solve certain types of problems and forming their economic thinking will allow them to positively solve problems that arise in their future work.

In the process of teaching economic sciences, taking into account the close connection between theory and practice, it is possible to use a wide range of teaching methods. But the most important condition for increasing the effectiveness of education in the process of studying is the balanced use of these methods.

The effectiveness of the educational process depends on certain factors, because the method of teaching economic sciences is aimed at ensuring the clarity and openness of the educational material, as well as a high theoretical level of teaching. Therefore, during the training process:

- Each highly educated specialist must communicate his plans and ideas to students and colleagues competently and at a high level;
- It is important for the teacher to have the ability to objectively analyze and separate economic problems and tasks from all political and ideological information;
- Persuasion means attraction, therefore, substantiation of the objectivity of the given information depends primarily on the competence, awareness and level of knowledge of the expert providing the knowledge;

One of the first tasks of the method in the teaching of economic sciences is the need for a relationship between theory and practice, because practice in economics requires confirmation of theory and practical justification. It must be acknowledged. All economic subjects are taught on the basis of common methodological requirements. However, it is desirable to use special methods that can reflect the specific features of the content of the subject in the teaching of separate subjects, because the content of the teaching of economic subjects depends on what methodology we use (picture).

Image. A set of didactic principles of applied methods Because methodology is not only a science and a scientific discipline, but also an active way of understanding modern economic reality.

Statistical data and reports of commercial organizations have been widely used in the teaching of economic sciences since ancient times. But nowadays, the non-use of comparative values in the data of the republic's statistics agency and enterprises creates great difficulties in studying and analyzing the activity of objects. This, in turn, reduces the objectivity of the results of the state of enterprises.

References:

1. Nazarova I.B. Teachers of economic discipline: professional potential, osobnosti zanyatosti i trudovoy motivatsii. - M.: MAKS Press, 2005.
2. Prakhov I.A. Teaching economics: is it an alternative lecture? //Voprosy obrazovaniya. - M., 2011. - #1.
3. Problems of economic education. URL: <http://www.economicus.ru>.
4. Khasevich N.P., Sakovich M.V. Methodology of economic teaching Discipline: ucheb. –method. complex. - 2006g.
5. Yarygina N.A. Sovremennye trebovaniya k prepodavaniyu ekonomicheskix discipline // Vector science TGU. Ser.: Pedagogy, psychology. – 2012. – #2.S. 352–355